

Investigation of Mapping Techniques in Adaptive Angular Discretization for the Discrete-Ordinate Method

Yuta Yoshiike^{1*}, Go Chiba¹, Jun-Shuang Fan¹

¹Hokkaido University, Sapporo, Japan

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ABSTRACT

The moment preservation conditions in adaptive angular discretization (AAD) for the discrete-ordinate method were examined. AAD enables high-precision angular discretization only where necessary, thereby improving the computational efficiency of neutron transport calculations. For mapping angular neutron flux between regions applying different angular grid points, either Lagrange interpolation or Legendre polynomial expansion was used. In the Lagrange interpolation approach, correction factors were applied to preserve selected angular moments, while the Legendre polynomial expansion inherently preserves these moments. Through the numerical tests, it was confirmed that the Legendre polynomial expansion is mathematically equivalent to the case where all moments are preserved following Lagrange interpolation. Various combinations of moments from 0th to 3rd order were also tested to evaluate their effects on computational accuracy. The results showed that preserving all moments up to the 3rd orders using Lagrange interpolation significantly improved the accuracy of the scalar neutron flux.

Keywords: Neutron transport equation, Discrete-ordinate method, Adaptive angular discretization, Moment preservation

1. INTRODUCTION

The neutron transport equation can be solved using two general approaches: probabilistic methods and deterministic methods. Although probabilistic methods with small approximation errors have become widely used in recent years, deterministic methods remain effective for design calculations, parameter studies, sensitivity analyzes, and uncertainty assessments that require a large number of calculation cases, as they can provide accurate solutions with limited computational resources.

The discrete-ordinate (SN) method is one of the most common deterministic approaches for solving the neutron transport equation in reactor core and shielding analyses. In this method, discrete angular points representing neutron directions are defined, and the transport equation is solved for each direction. Increasing the number of angular points improves accuracy by reducing discretization errors but also increases computational cost and memory usage.

Problems involving dilute regions with localized neutron sources or media with strong anisotropic scattering require a large number of angular points. In the former, the ray effect causes spatial oscillations when the number of directions is insufficient. In the latter, accurate evaluation of the scattering source term expanded in Legendre polynomials or spherical harmonics functions requires sufficient angular resolution. Therefore, developing models and algorithms that can efficiently achieve high-accuracy solutions is essential.

In the field of numerical computation, adaptive mesh discretization is widely used as an effective method for solving problems that require locally detailed discretization. Rather than discretizing the entire problem uniformly, this method distinguishes between regions that require detailed discretization

*watanabe.yuuta.w9@elms.hokudai.ac.jp

and those that do not, and it adjusts the discretization accuracy accordingly. Its application to spatial discretization is known as adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) and is being researched in fields such as reactor physics and computational fluid dynamics. The application of this to angular discretization is known as adaptive angular discretization (AAD). Research on AAD has been conducted by groups at the University of Florida and Texas A&M University, focusing on the adaptive refinement of angular discretization by region and on the development of high-precision angular integration sets [1–6].

In AAD, the mapping of angular neutron flux between regions applying different angular points significantly affects computational accuracy and efficiency. Generally, it is desirable to perform mapping in a way that preserves the distribution and moments of the angular neutron flux, and previous studies have also considered this perspective [4–6]. If errors can be minimized when mapping from high-dimensional angular flux to low-dimensional flux, and conversely, if accuracy can be improved when mapping from low-dimensional to high-dimensional flux, the practicality of AAD will be further enhanced.

In this study, we investigate methods to improve the mapping accuracy of angular neutron flux using a simple one-dimensional slab problem as an example. Specifically, we apply a moment conservation correction to the mapping using Lagrange interpolation and evaluate which moments should be conserved.

2. NUMERICAL THEORY

2.1. Neutron Transport Equation for a One-Dimensional Slab System

The dependence of the scattering cross section Σ_s on the scattering angle θ_0 is expanded in terms of the cosine of the scattering angle $\mu_0 = \cos \theta_0$ using Legendre polynomials $P_l(\mu_0)$ as follows;

$$\Sigma_s(\mu_0) = \sum_l \frac{2l+1}{2} \Sigma_{s,l} P_l(\mu_0). \quad (1)$$

Also, for a one-dimensional slab system, the neutron flux $\psi(x, \mu)$ directed at an angle μ relative to the cosine of the polar angle at spatial position x is expanded in terms of the Legendre polynomial $P_l(\mu)$ as follows;

$$\psi(x, \mu) = \sum_l \frac{2l+1}{2} \phi_l(x) P_l(\mu). \quad (2)$$

Here, the Legendre moment $\phi_l(x)$ of the neutron flux is defined as follows;

$$\phi_l(x) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^{+1} \psi(x, \mu) P_l(\mu) d\mu. \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) can be expressed using Gauss integration as follows;

$$\phi_l(x) \approx \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \omega_i P_l(\mu_i) \psi(x, \mu_i). \quad (4)$$

Having defined $\Sigma_{s,l}(x)$ and $\phi_l(x)$ as above, the neutron transport equation for a one-dimensional slab system is described as follows;

$$\mu \frac{d\psi(x, \mu)}{dx} + \Sigma_t(x) \psi(x, \mu) = \sum_{l=0}^L (2l+1) P_l(\mu) \Sigma_{s,l}(x) \phi_l(x) + S(x, \mu). \quad (5)$$

Here, $\Sigma_t(x)$ is the total cross section, and $S(x, \mu)$ is the external neutron source. When the external neutron source is isotropic, $S(x, \mu) = \frac{1}{2} S(x)$.

2.2. Mapping

In AAD used in this study, calculations are performed using a different number of angular divisions for regions requiring detailed discretization and regions that do not. In AAD, mapping between different angle divisions greatly affects calculation accuracy and efficiency.

In regions that use different angular discretizations, the number of direction cosines μ differs, resulting in different numbers of elements in the angular neutron flux $\psi(x, \mu)$ at position x .

The mapping process involves a balance between preserving the shape and conserving the angular moments. In this study, two mapping approaches were examined: Lagrange interpolation and Legendre polynomial expansion. Note that in this study, when the obtained angular neutron flux was negative, it was replaced with zero.

2.2.1. Mapping Using Lagrange Interpolation and Correction Using Angular Flux Moment

Mapping using Lagrange interpolation is expressed by the following equation;

$$\psi(x, \mu) = \sum_i \psi(x, \mu_i) \frac{\prod_{k \neq i} (\mu - \mu_k)}{\prod_{k \neq i} (\mu_i - \mu_k)}. \quad (6)$$

Calculations are performed independently for $0 < \mu < 1$ and $-1 < \mu < 0$.

While Lagrange interpolation preserves the overall shape, it does not guarantee moment conservation. Hence, correction factors are introduced to preserve the moments that are considered important. In the previous work[7], only the partial neutron flux (1st moment) is conserved, so no angular dependence arises in the correction factor. In this study, in order to conserve several different moments, angular dependence is introduced into the correction factor. The m th moment is expressed by the following equation.

$$\int \mu^m \psi(x, \mu) d\mu \approx \sum_{j=1}^J \omega_j \mu_j^m \psi(x, \mu_j) \quad (0 < \mu < 1 \quad \text{or} \quad -1 < \mu < 0). \quad (7)$$

In this study, the moment is defined as a partial moment. At a given spatial position, two different moments are calculated over distinct integration ranges.

For mappings from regions with fine angle divisions to regions with coarse angle divisions, the following correction is introduced. Let the cosine and weight in the region with a large number of angle divisions be μ^H, ω^H , and let the cosine and weight in the region with a small number of angle divisions be μ^L, ω^L . Let the correction factor be denoted as $1 + f_i$. The conservation equation for the m th moment is expressed as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^I \{ \omega_i^L (\mu_i^L)^m \psi(x, \mu_i^L) \cdot (1 + f_i) \} = \sum_{j=1}^J \omega_j^H (\mu_j^H)^m \psi(x, \mu_j^H). \quad (8)$$

Next, we consider conserving moments from the 0th up to the M th order. Define the matrix A and vector b as follows;

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_1^L (\mu_1^L)^0 \psi(x, \mu_1^L) & \omega_2^L (\mu_2^L)^0 \psi(x, \mu_2^L) & \cdots & \omega_I^L (\mu_I^L)^0 \psi(x, \mu_I^L) \\ \omega_1^L (\mu_1^L)^1 \psi(x, \mu_1^L) & \omega_2^L (\mu_2^L)^1 \psi(x, \mu_2^L) & \cdots & \omega_I^L (\mu_I^L)^1 \psi(x, \mu_I^L) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \omega_1^L (\mu_1^L)^M \psi(x, \mu_1^L) & \omega_2^L (\mu_2^L)^M \psi(x, \mu_2^L) & \cdots & \omega_I^L (\mu_I^L)^M \psi(x, \mu_I^L) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{b} = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^J \omega_j^H (\mu_j^H)^0 \psi(x, \mu_j^H) \\ \sum_{j=1}^J \omega_j^H (\mu_j^H)^1 \psi(x, \mu_j^H) \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{j=1}^J \omega_j^H (\mu_j^H)^M \psi(x, \mu_j^H) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

An angle-dependent correction factor vector \mathbf{f} is defined as

$$\mathbf{f} = \begin{pmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \\ \vdots \\ f_I \end{pmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

then the condition for preserving higher-order moments is expressed by the following equation;

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{e}, \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{e} is a vector whose entries are all unity. Each row of the matrix corresponds to the order of the moment to be preserved and can be selected arbitrarily. When the number of preserved moments is smaller than the number of low-order angular divisions, the correction factor cannot be uniquely determined. Therefore, to minimize the quantity of correction, the correction factor f_i is obtained using the pseudo-inverse matrix \mathbf{A}^\dagger , as

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{A}^\dagger (\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{e}), \quad (13)$$

and the angle-dependent neutron flux is then corrected using the following equation;

$$\psi'(x, \mu_i^L) = \psi(x, \mu_i^L) \cdot (1 + f_i). \quad (14)$$

When the number of preserved moments is equal to the number of lower-order angular divisions, the correction factor is uniquely determined and given by

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{e}. \quad (15)$$

If matrix \mathbf{A} contains zero angular neutron flux components, matrix \mathbf{A} becomes singular. In such a case, a least-squares solution can be obtained using the pseudoinverse; however, this situation does not arise in practical calculations.

2.2.2. Mapping Using Legendre Polynomials

For mappings from regions with fine angular divisions to regions with coarse angular divisions, mapping using Legendre polynomials is performed as follows. In this method, moment conservation is guaranteed; however, the shape is not preserved.

First, for the angular neutron flux $\psi(\mu)$ defined on $[0, 1]$, introduce the transformation $\hat{\mu} = 2\mu - 1$ to replace it with the function $\psi(\hat{\mu})$ defined on $[-1, 1]$. We assume that $\psi(\hat{\mu})$ can be expanded in Legendre polynomials as follows:

$$\psi(\hat{\mu}) = \sum_l \frac{2l+1}{2} a_l P_l(\hat{\mu}). \quad (16)$$

The expansion coefficients a_l are defined as follows;

$$a_l = \int_{-1}^1 P_l(\hat{\mu}) \psi(\hat{\mu}) d\hat{\mu} = 2 \int_0^1 P_l(2\mu - 1) \psi(\mu) d\mu. \quad (17)$$

Furthermore, using the Double Gauss–Legendre quadrature set, a_l can be calculated as follows:

$$a_l = 2 \sum_i \omega_i P_l(2\mu_i - 1) \psi(\mu_i), \quad (18)$$

where μ_i and ω_i are the integration points and weights, respectively, on $[0, 1]$.

Once the coefficients a_l are obtained in this manner, $\psi(\mu)$ at any μ can be determined as follows;

$$\psi(\mu) = \psi(\hat{\mu}) = \sum_l \frac{2l+1}{2} a_l P_l(\hat{\mu}) = \sum_l \frac{2l+1}{2} a_l P_l(2\mu - 1). \quad (19)$$

For $\psi(\mu)$ defined on the interval $[-1, 0]$, the transformation $\hat{\mu} = 2\mu + 1$ can be introduced, allowing computation via a similar procedure. This method is mathematically equivalent to the calculation performed when all possible moments are preserved after applying Lagrange interpolation because the Legendre polynomial expansion inherently preserves these moments.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Calculation Condition

This study describes the scattering cross section using the Henyey–Greenstein (HG) phase function, defined as follows:

$$\Sigma_s(\mu) = \Sigma_s \cdot \frac{1 - g^2}{2(1 + g^2 - 2g\mu)^{\frac{3}{2}}}. \quad (20)$$

Here, $\Sigma_s = \int \Sigma_s(\mu) d\mu$ and g is a parameter representing the anisotropy of scattering, corresponding to the cosine of the mean scattering angle. Expanding the scattering cross section defined in this way in terms of Legendre polynomials gives the following relationship: $\Sigma_{s,l}(x) = \Sigma_s(x) g^l$.

In implementing the numerical solution, mapping between different angular divisions requires special consideration of the algorithmic structure. Specifically, when performing the mapping, all angular neutron fluxes at positions where $0 < \mu < 1$ (or $-1 < \mu < 0$) are required. Therefore, in the SN method algorithm, the spatial loop must be placed on the outside and the angular loop on the inside.

The calculation conditions are shown in Figure 1. The numerical calculation was performed using a one-dimensional slab system. The total thickness was 100 cm, the boundary condition was reflective, and the spatial domain was divided into 800 meshes. The total cross section and the isotropic scattering cross section were set to 0.1 cm^{-1} and 0.05 cm^{-1} , respectively. The external neutron source was assumed to exist only in the region $[49, 51]$ cm, near the center of the system. Furthermore, the region $[40, 60]$ cm was designated as the domain requiring detailed angular discretization, and two conditions were considered: *a medium with strong anisotropic scattering* (Case 1), and *a medium without scattering* (isotropic scattering cross section is zero, Case 2). The value of g in the HG function was set to 1 in Case 1, and the Legendre expansion was carried out up to the 5th order. In addition, the region $[40, 60]$ cm or $[30, 70]$ cm were treated with 70 discrete angular directions (S70), while the remaining region was treated with S4. Therefore, up to four moments can be preserved in the mapping from S70 flux to S4 flux. The reference solution calculated over the entire domain with S70. Note that a Double Gauss-Legendre set was used.

Figure 1. Calculation condition

3.2. Comparison Based on Preserved Moment Conditions

The computational results using Lagrange interpolation with moment preservation are shown. Calculations were performed while preserving only the 1st order moment or the 0th plus 1st order moment, among others.

We also compared calculations performed after applying Lagrange interpolation with corrections to preserve all moments against calculations using Legendre polynomials. The calculation results confirmed the equivalence of the two methods.

The relative errors compared to the reference solution are shown in Figures 2 and 3. Since the system is symmetric about the center, only the results for the left half are shown. In Case 1 when handling the region $[40, 60]$ cm with S70, the results obtained by preserving the moments $(0, 1, 2)$ and $(0, 1, 3)$ overlap with the results obtained by preserving the moment $(0, 1, 2, 3)$. At the locations where the mapping is performed, preserving the 0th and 1st moments suppresses the error, and preserving higher-order moments further reduces the error at positions away from the mapping region. Across the entire domain, the smallest relative error is achieved by preserving all moments from 0th to 3rd order.

Next, the values of the correction factors $1 + f_i$ for each moment condition are shown in Figures 4 and 5. The greater the deviation of the correction factor from unity, the larger the difference from the angular neutron flux obtained via Lagrange interpolation. When preserving all moments from 0th to 3rd order, the correction factors deviate far from unity. However, as shown in Figures 2 and 3, it can be seen that high computational accuracy is achievable even when the angular neutron flux differs from the Lagrange interpolation results, provided that appropriate correction factors are selected.

Figure 2. Relative error in scalar neutron flux (S70: 40-60 cm, Left: Case 1, Right: Case 2)

Figure 3. Relative error in scalar neutron flux (S70: 30-70 cm, Left: Case 1, Right: Case 2)

Figure 4. Correction factor for angular neutron flux (S70: 40-60 cm, Left: Case 1, Right: Case 2)

Figure 5. Correction factor for angular neutron flux (S70: 30-70 cm, Left: Case 1, Right: Case 2)

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the effect of angular neutron flux mapping methods on computational accuracy in adaptive angular discretization for neutron transport calculations. The results demonstrated that, when using Lagrange interpolation combined with moment conservation correction, preserving all moments yields the highest accuracy. Furthermore, the comparison between the Lagrange interpolation method with full moment preservation and the mapping method using Legendre polynomials confirmed that the two approaches are mathematically equivalent.

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